

European criteria for a European degree (label)		European Approach
Not covered by European Approach		Partly covered
		Fully covered by European Approach
Higher education institutions involved	The joint programme is offered by at least 2 higher education institutions from at least 2 different Member States.	Definitions: Joint programmes are understood as an integrated curriculum coordinated and offered jointly by different higher education institutions from EHEA countries ¹ [...]
Transnational joint degree delivery	The joint programme is jointly designed and jointly delivered by all the higher education institutions involved.	1.2 Joint design and delivery: The joint programme should ² be offered jointly, involving all cooperating institutions in the design and delivery of the programme.
	The joint programme leads to the award of a joint degree.	(EA also “allows” double/multiple degree)
	EQF 6, 7: A joint Diploma Supplement is issued to the student at the end of the joint study programme.	(not specified, thought to “go without saying”)
Joint arrangements	EQF 6, 7: The joint programme describes the learning outcomes and credits in line with the ECTS Users Guide.	3.2 Credits: The European Credit Transfer System (ECTS) should be applied properly and the distribution of credits should be clear.
	The joint programme has joint policies, procedures and/or arrangements defining curriculum planning and delivery, as well as all organisational and administrative matters.	1.2 Joint design and delivery: The joint programme should ³ be offered jointly, involving all cooperating institutions in the design and delivery of the programme. 1.3 Cooperation Agreement: The terms and conditions of the joint programme should be laid down in a cooperation agreement. The agreement should in particular cover the following issues: Coordination and responsibilities of the partners involved regarding management and financial organisation (including funding, sharing of costs and income etc.) [...] Examination regulations, student assessment methods, recognition of credits and degree awarding procedures in the consortium.
Quality assurance arrangements	Students’ representatives are part of the decision-making process to define the joint policies and procedures and/or arrangements.	
	Internal and external Quality Assurance is conducted in accordance with the [ESG]. The higher education institutions, the study field or the programme are evaluated by an EQAR-registered agency (EA).	9. Quality Assurance [ESG 1.1 & part 1]: The cooperating institutions should apply joint internal quality assurance processes in accordance with part one of the ESG.
	The joint programme is evaluated using the standards of the European approach for quality assurance of joint programmes (EA).	(as a whole)

¹ The European Approach relates only to joint programmes offered jointly by higher education institutions from two or more countries, and does not address the quality assurance of programmes delivered jointly by different institutions from a single country.

² The Standards use of the common English usage of “should” which has the connotation of prescription and compliance.

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Graduate tracking	The joint programme monitors graduates through a graduate tracking system.	
Student-centred learning	The joint programme is designed and continuously enhanced and delivered in a way that encourages students to take an active role in the learning process. Assessment of students reflects this approach.	(not in EA, but ESG 1.3)
Interdisciplinarity	The joint programme includes embedded interdisciplinarity components.	
Labour market relevance	The joint programme aligns with labour market requirements by incorporating intersectoral components or activities ⁴ and the development of transversal skills.	2.2 Disciplinary field: The intended learning outcomes should comprise knowledge, skills, and competencies in the respective disciplinary field(s). 2.4 Regulated Professions: If relevant for the specific joint programme, the minimum agreed training conditions specified in the European Union Directive 2005/36/EC, or relevant common trainings frameworks established under the Directive, should be taken into account.
Digital skills	The joint programme includes components and actions related to the development of advanced digital skills of students, tailored to the capacities and circumstances of the joint programme, ensuring alignment with its scope and scholarly focus.	
Transnational campus – access to services	The programme has joint policies for students and staff to have access to relevant services in all participating higher educational institutions under equivalent conditions as all enrolled students and local staff.	6. Student Support [ESG 1.6]: The student support services should contribute to the achievement of the intended learning outcomes. They should take into account specific challenges of mobile students. 7.2 Facilities: The facilities provided should be sufficient and adequate in view of the intended learning outcomes
Flexible and embedded student mobility	<i>EQF 6,7</i> : The joint programme offers deep intercultural experience, including a minimum of 1 period of student physical mobility (that can be split in several stays) at one or more partner institution(s) representing overall at least 60 ECTS at EQF 6 level and 30 ECTS at EQF 7 level. The joint programme has a policy offering alternatives for students who are unable to travel.	
	<i>EQF 8</i> : The joint programme offers deep intercultural experience, including a total of at least 6 months of physical mobility at one or more partner institution(s). The joint programme has a policy offering alternatives for students who are unable to travel.	
Co-evaluation	<i>EQF 8</i> : Dissertations are supervised by at least 2	

⁴ Intersectoral components and activities include, but are not limited to, elements such as cooperation with economic and social sectors in curricula design and implementation, internships, work-based learning, secondment / placement, volunteering, service learning, challenge-based approaches.

and co-supervision for dissertations	supervisors and co-evaluated by co-supervisors or a committee with members from at least 2 different institutions located in 2 different countries.	
Democratic values	The joint programme's joint policies promote and adhere to democratic values.	
Multilingualism	During the joint programme, each student is exposed to at least 2 different EU languages.	
Inclusiveness and sustainability	The joint programme commits to wide participation by fostering diversity, equality, and inclusion and by adopting tailored measures to support students and staff with fewer opportunities.	5.1 Learning and teaching: [...] The diversity of students and their needs should be respected and attended to, especially in view of potential different cultural backgrounds of the students.
	<i>EQF 8:</i> The joint programme commits to respect the principles of the European Charter for Researchers.	
Green transition	The joint programme has policies and actions related to environmental sustainability and implements measures to minimise the environmental footprint of its activities	

Key changes between draft (used in pilots) and final (annex to proposed Council Recommendation):

<p>“Upgraded” from optional to required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> labour market relevance green skills digital skills democratic values, but less specific requirement now 	<p>Added:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> student-centred learning 	<p>Removed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> in multilingualism/exposure to languages, “language classes excluded” – hence these qualify now remaining optional criteria, i.e. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> virtual/blended learning language classes specifically internships/work-based learning career development plans joint promotion and awareness-raising activities
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